

Short communication

First records of *Leptoglossus occidentalis* Heidemann, 1910 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Coreidae) in Estonia and Belarus

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Abstract. The first records of *Leptoglossus occidentalis* Heidemann, 1910 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Coreidae: Coreinae: Anisoscelini) for Estonia and Belarus are reported. Information on the distribution of the species in Europe, in particular in its northern part, is summarized.

Key words: true bugs, Coreoidea, western conifer seed bug, distribution, new record, invasive species, Baltic states, Scandinavia.

Over the past two decades, the highly dispersible Nearctic coreid *Leptoglossus occidentalis* Heidemann, 1910 has colonized nearly all of Europe (van der Heyden 2019, 2020a, 2020b; van der Heyden & Zettel 2019).

So far, in Scandinavia the species has been reported from Denmark (Buhl & Stephensen 2009), Norway (Mjøs et al. 2010), Sweden (Lindelöw & Bergsten 2012) and Finland (van der Heyden 2020a). From the Baltics, *L. occidentalis* has only been reported from Lithuania (Karalius & Karaliūtė 2019) up to now. The presence of the species in other Baltic countries and Belarus has been expected (van der Heyden 2020a).

Now, the presence of *L. occidentalis* in Estonia and Belarus can be reported:

On 25.09.2020, Timo Pettay photographed an adult specimen of *L. occidentalis* on the island of Saaremaa in the Baltic Sea. A photograph of the specimen and specific data on this finding were uploaded to the online database eElurikkus (2020).

On 20.10.2020, an adult specimen of *L. occidentalis* was photographed near the town of Biaroza, located in the south-western part of Belarus. A photograph of the specimen was uploaded to the online database iNaturalist by Vadim Protasevich under the pseudonym naturalist46148 (Protasevich, 2020).

The records of *L. occidentalis* reported in this note are the first ones for Estonia and Belarus.

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